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PMMA/CeO₂ nanocomposites prepared by phase transfer synthesis protocol

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Abstract: Nanocomposites (NCs) were developed based on the polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) polymer matrix and filled with surface modified cerium oxide (CeO₂) nanoparticles. Different synthesis methodologies for CeO₂ nanoparticles and functionalization schemes of nanoparticle surfaces were evaluated using *ex-situ* and *in-situ* methodologies. For NC films synthesis, direct mixing and solvent evaporation were used in different protocols of nanoparticles incorporation on polymer matrix, remarking the protocol based on phase transfer, using palmitic acid (C₁₆H₃₂O₂) as a ligand of CeO₂ nanoparticles. To characterize the properties of the samples produced, thermogravimetry (TGA), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), infrared absorption spectrum (FTIR), and powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) studies were carried out. The PMMA/CeO₂ NC films were compared with pure PMMA films, indicating that, thermally, the NC maintains the main characteristics of the PMMA matrix. The glass transition temperature of NCs varies according to the surface functionalization applied to the nanoparticles. By XRD, when there is adequate incorporation and dispersion of the nanoparticles, the characteristic peaks of the CeO₂ crystalline planes could be observed in the NCs.

1. Introduction

There has been an increasing interest in technological applications for nanocomposite (NC) functionalized coatings due to the potential and exclusive physical and chemical properties of this materials class. Nanotechnology, inside this scenario, has great potential for the improvement of polymeric matrices properties, through selected nanoparticles incorporation, thus forming the NCs [1,2]. NCs are well known for their interesting optical, thermal, mechanical and conductivity properties, resulting from the synergistic interaction of the polymer

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with the nanometric structure. They are widely used in many applications such as dielectric ceramics, electrochromic devices, biosensors, corrosion protection, supercapacitors, and optoelectronic devices [3, 4, 5, 6, 7]. Also, the polymeric NCs use has already been a reality in the coatings industry and its commercial impact is expected to increase considerably [8].

The recent advances achieved for acrylic NC coatings, especially in terms of low electrolyte permeation, strong substrate adhesion, thermal stability, mechanical resistance, and high durability in harsh environments, have made them a potential alternative to conventional coating systems used in the automotive and aeronautical industry, construction, offshore facilities [9]. Especially anticorrosive coatings must be able to provide an effective physical barrier, which impede access of aggressive species to the metallic interface and for this purpose several materials have been applied including organic, inorganic and, recently, organic-inorganic hybrid [10]. Among the inorganic corrosion inhibitors, non-toxic cerium salts have been reported as the most active and cerium compounds added to organic-inorganic hybrid coatings have shown promising results due to cathodic protection provided by Ce^{+3} and Ce^{+4} ions [8].

In this work, NCs (organic-inorganic hybrid) were developed based on the polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) polymer matrix and filled with surface modified cerium oxide (CeO_2) nanoparticles intending to contribute to a future functionalization of this NC as an anticorrosive coating for industrial application.

2. Methodology

The PMMA/ CeO_2 NC synthesis protocol has considered direct mixture by magnetic stirring of commercially available PMMA powder (solvent solubilized) to provide cerium oxide nanoparticles incorporation. By solvent evaporation, in a process of at least 48 hours, the desired NC film can be obtained.

CeO_2 nanoparticles were synthesized by chemical precipitation route. The process of nanoparticles functionalization was subdivided into: (i) *ex-situ*: where the nanoparticles are first obtained and then the reaction with the surface-modifying surfactant is carried out; (ii) *in-situ*: in which the reaction with the surface-modifying surfactant agent occurs in the same process of nanoparticles synthesis [11].

2.1. Reagents and materials

The following reagents and materials were used: deionized water; $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ P.A (99%) by Sigma Aldrich; $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_2$ P.A. (99.5%) by Neon; CH_3COOH P.A – ACS (99.7%) by Dinâmica Química Contemporânea; Triton X-100 ($\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O})_n$) by Neon; DSS ($\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{25}\text{NaO}_4\text{S}$) 95% by Êxodo Científica; CHCl_3 P.A (99.8%) by ACS Científica; polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) Acrigel ECL[®], kindly donated by Unigel Plásticos S.A.

2.2. CeO_2 nanoparticles (ex-situ functionalized) synthesis

For the chemical precipitation route, $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was used as precursor and NH_4OH as precipitating agent, through an adaptation of the experiment proposed by Barbosa [12]. The $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2.17g) was dissolved in deionized water (50 mL) under vigorous magnetic stirring for 30 minutes. Then, 25 mL of NH_4OH aqueous solution (1 mol/L) was slowly added (drop by drop) to the previous solution and kept under magnetic stirring until it reached pH 10. Precipitate was collected after centrifugation (3000 rpm) and four-time washing with distilled water to eliminate undesirable salts. Then the sample is taken into the oven at a temperature of 80°C for 12 hours to dry.

Finally, dry powders are macerated. The *ex-situ* functionalization of the nanoparticles obtained by this route has consisted of their magnetic stirring in the surfactant solution used: Triton X-100 (non-ionic), DSS (anionic) or CH₃COOH (carboxylic group).

2.3. PMMA/CeO₂ (ex-situ functionalized) NCs synthesis

The first step towards the PMMA/CeO₂ (*ex-situ* functionalized) NCs synthesis was to solubilize the polymer as received (powder) in the chosen solvent (chloroform). This process has carried out under slow magnetic stirring for 24 hours to obtain a homogeneous and bubble-free matrix. The next step is to perform the direct mixture to incorporate the CeO₂ nanoparticles into the solubilized polymer, keeping the solution under magnetic stirring for more 4 hours. Then, the PMMA/CeO₂ solution is poured into the mold for casting and drying at room temperature for 48 hours to form a film.

2.4. PMMA/CeO₂ (in-situ functionalized) NCs synthesis

For the PMMA/CeO₂ NC synthesis procedure with *in-situ* functionalization, a protocol was developed based on phase transfer, using hexadenoic acid (C₁₆H₃₂O₂) known as “palmitic acid”, a long-chain representative of the carboxylic acid group. In this protocol, palmitic acid has the function of connecting and modifying the surface of cerium oxide nanoparticles. By phase transfer, there is selectivity from a solvent functional group towards the superficially modified CeO₂, which allows the transfer of nanoparticles from the aqueous phase to the organic phase and, later, their incorporation into the polymer matrix. This protocol consists in: (i) chemical precipitation; (ii) *in-situ* functionalization; (iii) phase transfer; (iv) phase separation; (v) matrix preparation and nanoparticles incorporation.

These are the detailed steps to obtain the PMMA/CeO₂ (*in-situ* functionalized) NCs: (i.1) Pour Ce(NO₃)₃.6H₂O solution (0.5 mol/L – 20 mL) in 25 mL of NH₄OH solution (1 mol/L), stirring with glass rod; (i.2) Warm the solution up to 80°C in a heating plate with magnetic stirring for 50 minutes; (ii.1) Add palmitic acid 0.05 g (3% of CeO₂ mol numbers) and stir for 1 hour in heating; (ii.2) Stop heating and continue stirring until cooling at room temperature; (ii.3) Filter to remove particulate matter excess; (iii.1) Add chloroform (20 mL) and keep stirring.

It is important to emphasize that in the (iii.1) stage, a separation of phases occurs: organic (containing chloroform) and aqueous (from the nanoparticles synthesis), being the inclusion of an organic phase to house CeO₂ nanoparticles essential for them to be incorporated into the PMMA, since it is completely hydrophobic. So, by chemical affinity, functionalized nanoparticles, which were previously in the aqueous phase, should migrate to the organic phase. This effect is experimentally observed by light scattering (Tyndall Effect), in which the laser beam propagates in the organic phase, indicating the migration of the nanoparticles to this phase.

Continuing the developed protocol: (iv.1) Separate the aqueous (inorganic) phase of the organic phase using a separation funnel, reserving the organic phase for the incorporation process; (v.1) Prepare PMMA/chloroform solution (10%) and keep in agitation for 24 hours; (v.2) Add the CeO₂ nanoparticles solution (organic phase) into the PMMA solution slowly and leave in magnetic stirring for more 3 hours; (v.3) Pour the PMMA/CeO₂ solution into a form or mold for solvent evaporation and drying at room temperature for 48 hours to form NC film.

2.5. Characterization

To characterize the PMMA/CeO₂ (*ex-situ* and *in-situ* functionalized) NCs, thermogravimetry (TGA/DTG), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), infrared absorption spectrum (FTIR), and powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) analyses were performed for some samples comparing them with the results for a pure PMMA film sample. For TGA, it was used SII Nanotechnology – Seiko, TG/DTA 6200 model, 100 mL min⁻¹ N₂ flow atmosphere, sample mass around 10 mg, platinum recipient and 10 °C min⁻¹ heat flow. For DSC, it was used TA Instruments Q20, sample mass around 10 mg, closed aluminum recipient, 10 °C min⁻¹ heat flow, 40 mL min⁻¹ N₂ flow atmosphere. For FTIR, it was used Spectrum 100 ATR Perkin-Elmer, 16 scanning, 4 cm⁻¹ resolution. For XRD, it was used Philips X'Pert MRD high-resolution diffractometer (Bragg-Brentano geometry).

3. Results and Discussions

Thermogravimetry (TGA/DTG) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) analyses results for PMMA/CeO₂ (*ex-situ* and *in-situ* functionalized) NCs are partially presented at Fig.1 (a) and (b). The used surfactants for *ex-situ* functionalization are, respectively: (i) Triton X-100 for NANOCOMP 1; (ii) DSS for NANOCOMP 2; (iii) acetic acid for NANOCOMP 3. For *in-situ* functionalization, the surfactant is the palmitic acid, and nanoparticles concentration was varied (0.5%; 1%; 2%).

By TGA/DTG, it is possible to observe that PMMA/CeO₂ NCs maintain the same behavior as pure PMMA film, in which two stages of material degradation are identified. There are no significant changes in the temperatures at degradation stages among the analyzed samples. Also, the mass loss at each stage of degradation was similar between the NCs and the pure PMMA film. The highest residue percentage at 500°C obtained for NC in relation to pure PMMA film indicates that CeO₂ nanoparticles were incorporated into the PMMA matrix, although the percentage varied indicating dispersion issues:

- *Ex-situ* functionalized analysis: 1.08% for NANOCOMP 1; 1.65% for NANOCOMP 2; 2.29% for NANOCOMP 3; 0.73% for pure PMMA film;
- *In-situ* functionalized analysis: 0.42% for NANOCOMP 0.5%_P; 1.17% for NANOCOMP 1%_P; 1.66% for NANOCOMP 2%_P; 0.14% for pure PMMA film.

By DSC, it was noted that glass transition temperatures (T_g) can be influenced by the surfactant or the NC concentration, remarking acetic acid decreased T_g and the highest concentration of palmitic acid increased T_g, what indicates possibility of obtaining better properties through an optimization of *in-situ* functionalization protocol.

By FTIR, NC films presented basically the same spectra as PMMA pure film, as Fig. 1 (c), considering the scanning among 650-4000cm⁻¹. Based on X-ray diffraction (XRD) analyses, it was possible to compare the curves of PMMA/CeO₂ (*ex-situ* and *in-situ* functionalized) NCs and their respective filling nanoparticles, as Fig. 1 (d). Only the NANOCOMP 2 curve, with CeO₂ nanoparticles functionalized with DSS, indicated the peaks related to cerium oxide (as ICSD 01-081-0792), which suggests the effective nanoparticles incorporation in the polymer base (PMMA). In the *in-situ* NANOCOMP 2%_P curve, the peaks could not be well defined, which indicates that there were problems in the incorporation and/or dispersion of the nanoparticles in this sample.

Fig.1. Curves for PMMA/CeO₂ *ex-situ* and *in-situ* functionalized NCs (a) TGA; (b) DSC; (c) FTIR; (d) XRD.

4. Conclusions

PMMA/CeO₂ NCs were synthesized using different protocols, emphasizing the developed *in-situ* functionalization protocol with palmitic acid, contributing to the studies for a future anticorrosive coating based on this material. The thermal behavior, structure and morphology were evaluated and compared with pure PMMA, evaluating the NCs characteristics. The results showed that both *ex-situ* and *in-situ* functionalization tested protocols have uncertainties regarding the adequate dispersion of CeO₂ nanoparticles, but *in-situ* functionalization protocol using carboxylic group acid is promising for this purpose. However, it is still necessary to refine the parameters used in this developed *in-situ* functionalization protocol to obtain a higher concentration of nanoparticles in the phase transfer stage. *Ex-situ* DSS functionalization presented satisfactory incorporation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

CRedit author statement

AECS Palazzo: Conceptualisation; Methodology; Formal Analysis; Writing – original draft. **RS Nunes:** Methodology; Resources; Supervision; Writing – review. **VP Murari:** Methodology. **CJ Dalmaschio:** Methodology; Writing – review. **EC Botelho:** Resources; Supervision; Writing – review.

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